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PRINCIPALS' TEAMWORK PRACTICES AND TEACHERS' ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract

The study determined the correlation between principals' teamwork practices and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted the correlational research design. The population of the study comprised 12,346 teachers in the 266 State government owned secondary schools in the state. A sample of 617 was drawn from the population using stage sampling procedure. A researcher developed instrument titled Teachers Principals' Teamwork Practices and Teachers' Organizational Citizenship Behaviour Questionnaire (PTPTOCBQ) which was validated by three experts was used for data collection. Reliability co-efficients indices of 0.80 and 0.88 was obtained for the two clusters of the instrument while the overall reliability index of 0.88 was obtained for the instrument using Cronbach Alpha. Out of 617 copies of the questionnaire administered on the respondents, 606 copies were duly completed, retrieved and used for data analysis. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The result of the study indicated that maintenance of a collaborative culture in which teachers engage in focused and purposeful development and collaborative decision making is essential in motivating teachers to perform above and beyond their minimum level which indicates teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour. It was also found out that teamwork brings the school personnel together and improves communication and the overall climate of the school. Based on the findings it is recommended among others that seminars and workshops on effective teamwork should be organized at intervals for principals.

Keywords:

Principal, Teamwork, Teacher, Organizational Citizenship Behaviour, Secondary schools.

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Introduction

The Nigerian educational system especially at the secondary school level is faced with ever growing demands like higher expectation regarding students' achievement, enhanced diversity in the classroom and demonstration of teamwork skills for the 21st century workforce. These demands make schools' success more and more dependent on teachers' willingness to go above and beyond the call of duty which is referred to as teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour. It further relies upon the heads of the schools who nurture the crop of teachers that embrace a mentality of going above and beyond job description. High quality teaching and high quality of leadership are very necessary for a successful education.

Secondary schools are saddled with the onerous responsibility of preparing the youth for useful living in the society through appropriate arrangement and implementation of the school curriculum. The business of managing such a curriculum has never been a one-man affair. It rather takes the collaborative efforts of the head of the school and the staff to achieve school goals and objectives (Ndu, 2013). This is to say that the teacher and the principal are important to one another and cannot work in isolation. No wonder, Uzonwanne (2014) identified strong and effective teams as a must have for every organization that seeks the peak of performance abilities. In other words, teamwork has been recognized as the means by which schools strive to achieve the stated goals.

Teamwork according to Mangi, Bundi and Mohammed (2015), refers to a group of human beings that have high performance with its members along with the spirit that enables them to achieve the group's goals in the workplace with confidence and co-operation and reduces the workload for everyone, which enables them to exchange ideas. Thus, teamwork practices is an effective leadership behaviour adopted by leaders to bridge the gap between superior subordinate relationship and providing an opportunity for every member of the organization to contribute brains and ingenuity to ensure physical organizational effectiveness. For schools to be successful, everyone must have clear shared goals, a sense of commitment, the ability to work together and other elements of teamwork.

Among the most important teamwork variables are clarity of goals, open communication, participative leadership, training, delegation to duty and empowerment (Ahmed & Al-Hawary, 2017, David, 2018; Duncan, 2017 & Meesad, 2013). This corroborates the findings of Ameneh and Nooshin, 2015, Amet, 2016, Arefi, Shohodi and Zandi, 2012, Oplatka and Stundi, 2011, Shouvik and Mohammed, 2018, that teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour is based on participative leadership, open communication, support for staff development, empowerment, delegation and clarity of goals. When school members share common goals, know their roles and responsibilities have open method of communication, share leadership and are motivated to perform, success is achieved. In tandem with this, Okorji (2014) and Ugurlu and Sincar (2013) submitted that the school needs an open, sound and flexible communication in order to influence the behaviours of teachers. This agrees with Unachukwu (2014) who argued that school leadership has continually shifted from command and control to building teams and getting people to work along with others through inspiration and vision. Therefore, the attainment of the school organizational objectives depends on the ability of the school principals in coordinating and creating a conducive and harmonious atmosphere among the human and material resources in the school, that is to say that the principal like any other administrator of an organization upholds a process of continuous striving for the total enhancement of the organizations' status.

The principal's behaviour should be perceived to be participative. According to Ike, Ezeh and Etodike (2017) participative leadership is the act of sharing power among individual members in the organization as a way of empowering them for superior performance. In relation to the school, this amounts to saying that principals' must be ready to give out part of their power to teachers in an exchange, in order to promote good citizenship behaviour among the teachers that is the idea of something for something as indicated in the social exchange theory.

Furthermore, superior-subordinate communication is an important influence on teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour (Herfina & Rubbin, 2015). When principals create an open door policy, guide and encourage teachers by communicating important information, teachers will be obliged to take risks inside and outside the classrooms for effective functioning of the school (Sportsmanship). Obviously, in an educational institution where this type of leadership behaviour prevails high commitment, harmony, mutual trust, job satisfaction and high performance in students' achievement may be experienced. Thus, one of the significant problems facing principals' today is to identify what contributes to teachers' lack of commitment to duty and the type of leadership behaviour principals' should employ to promote teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour.

Organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB), is doing the right thing that benefits the greater good of an organization without receiving recognition or merit. Active participation of employees beyond the normal demands of their work for organizational development and improvement is seen as organizational citizenship behaviour. Within the educational setting, teachers who voluntarily go out of their way to help their students, colleagues and others as they engage in the work of teaching and learning exemplify organizational citizenship behaviour. Teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour is therefore the efforts made by teachers to do extra things in the work environment.

Organ (1988), categorized organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) into five dimensions namely: altruism, courtesy, conscientiousness, sportsmanship and civic virtue. Altruism is voluntarily helping others in need without concern for one's own benefit or well-being. Altruistic behaviours have a positive impact on achievement of school goals and can be encouraged as well as discouraged based on the treatment given to subordinates. In schools it can be achieved if combined knowledge, expertise and experience of role players are harnessed in a collaborative manner.

The principal imperatively has a challenging task of encouraging sportsmanship behaviour among teachers. Sportsmanship is the principle of tolerance which must form part of every organizational frame work and is important for enhancing the morale of colleagues. Sportsmanship produces awareness among teachers that they should continue to struggle for the effectiveness of the school even if the higher authorities do not acknowledge or appreciate their efforts (Somech & Oplatka, 2014). Several authors are in agreement that conscientious behaviour are beyond role requirements, directed at the organization and exhibited as a matter of the conscience. Theoretically, conscientiousness may be an important predictor of work place behaviours because it provides directions and associations that are necessary to produce targeted behaviour. Andrew (2016) advanced that, this type of behaviour may manifest among teachers whose principals are supportive to their participation in decision making process. Teachers' have different levels of organizational citizenship behaviour.

The level of organizational citizenship behaviour in schools is mostly affected by intrinsic factors such as teachers' relationship with the principal, participative leadership, informative work environment and mentally challenging work among others. These behaviours are important and

cannot be ignored by any school principal as they affect both the academic excellence of the students and service level of the school. For Ikediugwu (2016), students' performance, teachers' achievement and schools' effectiveness all depends on the quality of the principal of the school. This supports Herren (2014) who suggested that the relationship between principals' leadership behaviour and their level of organizational citizenship behaviour indicates that teachers' performances are influenced by their perceptions of principals' leadership behaviour.

Contrary to the behaviours expected of the school administrators, some studies revealed that some school administrators do not apply these behaviours to a very great extent (Andrew, 2016; Ibara 2011; & Osakwe, 2014). Most principals isolate teachers from important administrative functions thereby asking them to wait for their own turn. In some schools in Anambra state which the researcher visited as a supervisor, some principals admit students by themselves without recourse or inputs by the vice principals, guidance counselor and heads of departments as against what is stipulated in the Education Quality Assurance Handbook (2010), concerning admission of students. In the same vein Awodumilla (2017); Ikegbusi (2016) and Oluremi (2013) submitted that many secondary school principals in Nigeria have no serious or professional training in educational management and administration and are therefore bereft of the changing trends in administration of the 21st century. Probably this could be the reason for the poor teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour observed in Nigerian secondary schools. Teachers on their own seem to neglect their duties and exhibit "I don't care attitude" towards educational improvement. Teachers often complained during world teachers' day (Daily trust, 2010), that they were not part of the decision making process of their school. As a result, many teachers seem to abandon classes, absent themselves from school, form cliques and easily leave the teaching jobs for greener pastures. Ameneh and Nooshin (2015), posit that poor teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour is at all times high and this may be seen in the form of absenteeism, low morale and an attitude of don't ask me to do a single extra thing.

Furthermore, from the observation of the researcher, as a principal in the state there is a tendency that not all teachers optimally engage in activities within their schools thus providing an initial assumption that OCB among secondary school teachers in Anambra State still seems to be low. Thus, principals should facilitate authentic participation by asking for the input of those affected by decisions, providing background information necessary for staff to weigh in on decisions, and treating teachers as capable professionals whose insights are valuable. The question that arises is, if there is a management style of the principals which can encourage teacher participation in decision making process. This necessitated this study which sought to empirically ascertain the correlation between teachers' perception of principal's participative and open communication teamwork practices and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

Two research questions guided the study namely;

1. What is the nature of correlation between teachers' perception of principals' use of participative leadership and teachers' organizational citizenship?
2. What is the nature of correlation between teachers' perception of principals' use of open communication and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour?

Hypotheses

Two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level significance namely;

1. Teachers' perception of principals' use of participative leadership will not significantly correlate with teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour.
2. Teachers' perception of principals' use of open communication will not significantly correlate with teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour.

Method

The research design adopted for this study is the correlational survey design. The study area is Anambra State. The population comprised all the 6, 382 teachers in the 261 state government owned secondary schools in the six education zones in the state namely Aguata, Awka, Ihiala, Nnewi, Ogidi and Otuocha education zones. The proportionate stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used to draw 689 teachers from the six education zones in the state. A researcher developed instrument titled "Teachers Principals' Teamwork Practices and Teachers' Organizational Citizenship Behaviour Questionnaire (PTPTOCBQ) which was validated by three experts was used for data collection. The instrument is made up of three parts, A and B. Part A is on principals' teamwork practices while Part B focused on Teachers' Organizational Citizenship Behaviour. The instrument was structured on a four point scale ranging of Strongly Disagree (SD), Disagree (D) Agree (A) and Strongly Agree (SA) weighted 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively. The internal consistency of the instrument was verified using Cronbach Alpha and it yielded a co-efficient of 0.80 and 0.88 for part A and B respectively while the overall coefficient of the instrument was 0.88. A total of 617 copies of the questionnaire were administered by the researchers and six research assistants. Out of 617 copies of the questionnaire administered on the respondents, 606 copies were duly completed, retrieved and used for data analysis. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to answer the research questions and to test the hypotheses AT 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 1: Pearson's correlation between teachers' perception of principals' use of participative leadership and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour

Source of Variation	N	Participative Leadership	Teachers' OCB	Remark
Participative Leadership	606	1.00	0.94	Very High Positive Relationship
Teachers' OCB	606	0.94	1.00	

The results in Table 1 show the Pearson's Correlation, $r = 0.94$. This shows that there is a very high positive correlation between teachers' perception of principals' use of participative leadership and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour. This indicates that if there is an increase in principals' use of participative leadership, teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour would also increase.

Table 2: Pearson's on teachers' perception of principals' use of open communication and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour

Source of Variation	N	Open Communication	Teachers' OCB	Remark
Open Communication	606	1.00	0.64	Substantial Positive

				Relationship
Teachers' OCB	606	0.64	1.00	

Results on table 2 indicate that there is a substantial positive relationship $r =$ of 0.64 between teachers' perception of principals' use of open communication and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour. The implication of this is that when principals create an open door policy, guide and encourage teachers by communicating important information, teachers will be obliged to take risks inside and outside the classrooms for effective functioning of the school (sportsmanship)

Table 3: Test of significance of Pearson's correlation between teachers' perception of principals' use of participative leadership and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour.

Source of Variation	N	Participative Leadership	Teachers' OCB	p-value	Remark
Participative Leadership	606	1.00	0.94	.000	Sig
Teachers' OCB	606	0.94	1.00		

Data analysis in Table 3 shows that there is a significant correlation between teachers' perception of principals' use of participative leadership and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour. $r, (606) = 0.94, P\text{-value } 0.00 < 0.05$. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Table 4: Test of significance of Pearson's Correlation between teachers' perception of principals' use of open communication and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour

Source of Variation	N	Open Communication	Teachers' OCB	p-value	Remark
Open Communication	606	1.00	0.64	.000	Sig
Teachers' OCB	606	0.64	1.00		

Data analysis displayed in Table 4 show that there is a significant correlation between teachers' perception of principals' use of open communication and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour, $r, (606) = 0.64, P\text{-value } 0.00 < 0.05$. The second null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that a significant positive relationship exist between principals' use of participative leadership and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour. This finding concurs with Ahmed and Al-Hawary (2017); Amet, (2016); Belogovsky and Somech, (2010); Ibara (2011) and Somech and Oplatka, (2014) who revealed that participative leadership is the form of leadership most closely associated with teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour. This entails that principals should facilitate authentic participation by asking for the input of those affected by decisions, providing background information necessary staff to weigh on decisions and treating teachers as capable professionals whose insight are valuable. Regarding the relationship between principals' use of participative leadership and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour Ike, Ezech

and Etodike (2017) reported that in order to increase organizational pro-social behaviour which has direct implication for performance and employee satisfaction at all levels, employee participation in decision making should be encouraged in organizations. This is also consistent with the findings of Agha, Nwakpa and Eze (2017), Oguz (2010); Q1 and Liu (2017); Runhaar, Konermann and Sanders (2013) who concluded that employees are satisfied with the implementation of modern administration in which the leader gives direction and then allows them complete freedom to accomplish the job. This is an indication that staff participation in decision making motivates teachers to go the extra mile in teaching and learning.

Regarding the relationship between principals' use of open communication and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour the study revealed that leaders open method of communication and organizational citizenship behaviour is significant. The findings support that Ugurlu and Sincar (2013) who concluded in their study on primary school teachers' views on communication skills and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour that the better the inter-personal communication then the higher the level of OCB and on the other hand the poorer the interpersonal communication the lower the level of OCB. To date, teamwork practices which encourage staff participation in decision making and open method of communication have been a highly acclaimed leadership style; therefore its positive relationship with teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour is not surprising.

Conclusion

The major findings of this study revealed that there is a positive and significant correlation between principals' teamwork practices and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in secondary schools in Anambra State. From the analysis and interpretation of results, it is concluded that principals' teamwork behaviour are capable of bringing about teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour. This also implies that the stability, survival and success of schools fundamentally depend on teachers' willingness to exceed their official job description through the help of participative principals.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Seminars and workshops on effective teamwork practices should be organized by the School Management Boards for Principals' from time to time.
2. Principals should make effort to ensure that their relationships with teachers are cordial by involving teachers in decision making of the school as this promotes teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour.

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